

On the Constitution of some Dinitro-*m*-cresols.

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There are contradictory statements regarding the constitution of the dinitro-*m*-cresols. A dinitro-*m*-cresol having m.p. 74° is described by Gibbs and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 106, 1889) to which the authors assign the constitution 1-methyl-3-hydroxy-2:6-dinitrobenzene. The same authors also describe another dinitro-*m*-cresol having a m.p. 60° and to this they ascribe the constitution 1-methyl-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene. Will who prepared a large number of isomeric trinitrotoluenes obtained from one of these a dinitro-*m*-cresol of the constitution 1-methyl-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene having the melting point 74° (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 712). Borsche starting from 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene obtained, by replacement of the chlorine atom by hydroxyl group, 1-methyl-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene which melted at 63°–65° (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1350).

From this brief summary it will be seen that two different dinitro-*m*-cresols are described in literature having the melting point 74°, while the dinitro-*m*-cresols described by Will and also by Borsche and having, according to these authors, the same constitution have different melting points.

In order to settle the constitution of these dinitro-*m*-cresols, the best method is to start from 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene the constitution of which has been proved beyond doubt (Reverdin and Crapieux, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2506). We consequently repeated Borsche's experiment and found that the product obtained by fusing 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene with sodium acetate and acetamide does not melt at 63–65° but at 74°. That there is no migration of groups during this fusion is proved by the fact that the dinitrotoluidine obtained from the *p*-toluene sulphonyl ester of this dinitro-*m*-cresol is identical with the 3-amino-4:6-dinitrotoluene obtained by heating 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene with ammonia. This dinitrotoluidine is also identical with the dinitrotoluidine, (m.p. 194°) from which Will prepared his 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (CH₃=1, OH=3). 1-Methyl-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene has therefore the melting point 74°.

The bromocompound obtained by the bromination of this dinitro-*m*-cresol has therefore the constitution 1-methyl-2-bromo-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene (m.p. 115°–116°). The chloro-compound which we have obtained from the latter compound by the replacement of the hydroxyl group by chlorine has therefore the constitution: 1-methyl-2-bromo-3-chloro-4:6-dinitrobenzene (m.p. 81°–82°). This last compound is identical with the chlorobromodinitrotoluene which Cohen and Smithells (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1909) obtained by nitrating 2:3-bromochlorotoluene. Gibbs and Robertson's 2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (m.p. 74°) is really 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (OH=1, CH₃=3) and their and probably also Kehrman's (*Annalen*, 1898, 303, 29) 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol is 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Methyl-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene was obtained from *m*-chlorotoluene as follows: A mixture of nitric acid (18 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (22 c.c.) was added gradually to *m*-chlorotoluene (12·6 g.). During nitration the mixture was cooled and well shaken and then left overnight. On adding water to this mixture 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrotoluene (18 g.) was obtained in pale white crystals, m.p. 91° (Reverdin and Crepieux, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2505). Chlorodinitrotoluene (9·5 g.) was then heated with a mixture of anhydrous sodium acetate (9·5 g.) and acetamide (28·5 g.) for an hour at 180°. On treating the mass with water, dinitro-*m*-cresol was obtained (5·5 g.). It was recrystallised from acetic acid: yellow crystals, m.p. 74°. (Found: N, 14·08. C₇H₆O₃N₂ requires N, 14·14 per cent.)

4:6-Dinitro-*m*-cresyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate (OH=1, CH₃=3).—4:6-Dinitro-*m*-cresol (4 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride (4·2 g.) and diethylaniline (8 c.c.) were heated on water-bath for four hours. From the dark product diethylaniline was removed by means of hydrochloric acid. On rubbing the residue with alcohol, the dinitro-*m*-cresylsulphonate separated out in crystalline form (5·6 g.). It dissolves easily in acetone and benzene, but is not easily soluble in alcohol. Colourless crystals from alcohol; m.p. 110°–111°. (Found: S, 9·21. C₁₂H₁₁O₃N₂S requires S, 9·11 per cent.)

1-Methyl-3-amino-4:6-dinitrobenzene (4:6-dinitrotoluidine).—Through the boiling solution of 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresylsulphonate (3·5 g.) in xylene, a current of dry ammonia was passed for about

an hour and xylene removed by means of steam. The residue was 4:6-dinitro-*m*-toluidine (1.3 g.); yellow crystals from acetic acid, m.p. 194°. (Found: N, 21.14. $C_7H_7O_2N_2$ requires N, 21.31 per cent.).

1-*Methyl-2-bromo-3-hydroxy-4:6-dinitrobenzene* (2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol: OH=1, CH₃=3).—This was obtained by adding bromine (1.1 c.c.) to a solution of 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (4 g.) in acetic acid. On adding a little water to the mixture, the bromo-dinitrocresol separated out. It is easily soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. Orange yellow crystals from acetic acid; m.p. 115°–116°. (Found: Br, 29.09. $C_7H_5O_2N_2Br$ requires Br, 28.85 per cent.).

3-*Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrotoluene*.—A mixture of 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (5.6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride (4.2 g) and diethylaniline (12 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for six hours. From the dark product the diethylaniline was removed by means of hydrochloric acid and the residue was shaken with sodium carbonate solution. The residue was then dissolved in alcohol and the solution boiled with animal charcoal. On concentrating the filtrate the chlorobromodinitrotoluene separated out. Easily soluble in most organic solvents; colourless crystals, m.p. 81°–82°. (Found: N, 9.19. $C_7H_4O_2N_2ClBr$ requires N, 9.48 per cent.).

